

Beaver Fever: A Neglected Zoonoses

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Abstract

Beaver Fever is characterised by stomach pains, nausea, bloating, and bouts of watery diarrhoea. It is also known as Giardiasis. *Giardia* infection is caused by a micro parasite that is present all over the world, particularly in places with inadequate sanitation and contaminated water. The parasites have been detected in rural streams and lakes, as well as public water supplies, whirlpool spas, swimming pool and wells. Food and person-to-person contact can both spread *Giardia* infection. Infection is removed within few weeks. However, even after the parasites have been removed, affected person experience digestive difficulties. Several medications are usually successful against *Giardia* parasites; however, they do not work for everyone. The best defence is prevention.

Introduction

Giardiasis is a protozoal enteric infection caused by the protozoa *Giardia duodenalis*. It causes a greater incidence of gastrointestinal diseases (giardiasis, often known as beaver fever) around the world; health consequences include diarrhoea, which leads to malabsorption and restricted growth in children. It is a prevalent condition in low-resource settings and is characterised by flatulence and watery diarrhoea. Globally, an estimated 280 million individuals are infected each year, with 1.2 million new cases recorded in the United States each year. In the western Canadian province of British Columbia, 627 new cases are recorded each year on average (BC). The disease is most commonly observed in international travellers, wilderness travellers, and day-care employees in the United States. Patients may have strong enough symptoms to cause dehydration and weight loss, even though they are asymptomatic. The prevalence rate of *Giardia* infection in India ranges from 0.4 percent to 70 percent in diarrhoeic patient, and asymptomatic cyst passage has been shown to be as high as 50% in rural southern India (Laishram *et al.*, 2012). The World Health Organization (WHO) has officially classified *Giardia* as a significant food-borne infection. The WHO's Neglected Diseases Initiative has also included giardiasis, with the purpose of offering more knowledge into protozoan biology, infection epidemiology, and host-parasite interactions (Tsui *et al.*, 2018). Organism is flagellated and discovered by Leeuwenhoek in 1681.

Etiology

Giardia spp. are flagellated protozoan parasites that may affect humans and animals' gastrointestinal tracts. *Giardia intestinalis*, a protozoal parasite of the *Hexamitidae* family (order Diplomonadida), causes giardiasis. *Giardia lamblia*, *Lambliia intestinalis*, and *Giardia duodenalis* are all names for this bacterium. The organisms isolated from domestic animals, wild animals and humans appear to be identical; although, *G. intestinalis* might be a complex containing several distinct species or subspecies. Individuals are known to be the primary source of infection for other humans. *G. intestinalis* interspecies transmission has been observed, and zoonotic transmission is suspected. However, the significance of animal reservoirs for human disease is debatable. Other *Giardia* species can be found in birds, amphibians, reptiles, and rodents. There is no data that these organisms are zoonotic. *Giardia muris* has been detected in rodents, birds, and reptiles. *Giardia agilis* may be found in amphibians.

Giardia cysts may live in the environment for long periods of time in cool, wet environments and for several months in cold water. It has been demonstrated that they can survive in water for 1 month at 21°C and 2 months at 8°C. Some cysts may last for two weeks if freezing at -13°C. Desiccation and direct sunshine are both destructive to *Giardia* cysts.

Transmission

Transmission can occur in three ways: water, food, person to person. There are two stages of parasite: cysts and trophozoites. Surface waters are especially likely to be contaminated from faeces from both human and animal sources. Cysts may infect humans as well as wild and domestic animals. In the small intestine, ingested cysts release one or two trophozoites, that multiply and most of those dividing trophozoites are transported to the colon, where they encyst. When the cysts are passed in the faeces or shortly thereafter, they become infectious. Trophozoites can also be detected in the faeces of an infected human or animal, particularly diarrheic faeces, and can contaminate water or food. Anal intercourse is a mode of transmission among humans.

Among wild animals, the beaver has received attention as an important source of *Giardia* contamination. Beavers (*Castor canadensis*), a water-dwelling animal, have been related to giardiasis transmission via water. Since beavers can excrete cysts in faeces directly into surface sources of animal and human drinking water, including lakes, rivers, and streams, zoonotic transmission of *Giardia* from beavers to humans has been suggested (Erlandsen *et al.*,

1988). People become infected after ingesting *Giardia* and can carry the parasite in their body for several weeks to months.

Pathophysiology

The etiology of symptoms in giardiasis is unspecified. Trophozoites have a ventral cycle that they utilize to attach to intestinal epithelial cells. The protozoa, according to researchers, alter small intestine epithelial cell connections as well as brush border enzymes. Patients who are affected may have altered gastrointestinal motility. Thiol proteinases and lectins are released by the protozoa and have a cytotoxic impact. The combination of these actions improves permeability while decreasing saccharide processing ability.

Infection in animals, *G. intestinalis* can be found in many wild and domestic animals, including dogs, cats and ruminants. Infections are infrequent in horses and pigs. Beavers might be a source of contamination in rivers. Incubation period is 5 - 14 days. The majority of infections, especially in older animals, are asymptomatic. Acute, chronic or intermittent diarrhoea may be seen in some puppies and kittens. The clinical signs can include diarrhoea or soft stools, a poor hair coat, flatulence, and weight loss or failure to gain weight. The stools are typically light-coloured and mucoid, and may contain undigested fat. Blood is rarely seen. Similar gastrointestinal symptoms have been described in other species, such as calves and lambs (Campbell, 2016).

Diagnosis

Microscopic examination of the stool is the most established diagnostic technique and remains a valuable technique in the evaluation of the patient with diarrhoea or suspected giardiasis. Microscopy sensitivity can be enhanced by collecting three stool samples on different days. Because standard ova and parasite laboratory testing does not necessarily include *Giardia* testing, the CDC recommends providers to explicitly request *Giardia* testing when submitting stool samples. There are stool antigen detection assays and nucleic acid amplification tests (NAAT) available, which are often faster, more sensitive, more specific than microscopy. Because the differential diagnosis for giardiasis includes other parasitic diseases, microscopy should be done even if antigen or NAAT tests are positive.

Treatment

Metronidazole (Flagyl) is a drug that is used to treat giardiasis. It given in doses of 250 mg three times a day for 7 days for adults and 5 mg/kg three times a day for 7 days for children. Cure rates are in the range of 85 to 95%. Side effects are rare, but they may include: convulsions, confusion, hallucinations, rash, nausea, metallic taste, dark or cloudy urine,

vomiting, and drowsiness. Metronidazole has the potential to interact with alcohol dehydrogenase, an enzyme that breaks down alcohol. As a result, drinking should be avoided throughout therapy. **Tinidazole (Tindamax)** works as well as metronidazole and often treats giardiasis in single dose. It is given to adults as a single 2gm dose and as a 30 to 35 mg/kg single dose to children. It has side effects too. **Nitazoxanide (Alinia)** Because it comes in a liquid form, nitazoxanide may be easier for children to swallow for three days. Side effects may include nausea, gas, yellow eyes and brightly coloured yellow urine. **Paromomycin** has a reduced risk of causing birth abnormalities than other antibiotics, but pregnant women should avoid taking any giardiasis medicine until after delivery. This medication is given at 500 mg, 3 times a day for 5-10 days (Lebwohl *et al.*, 2003).

Prevention

- Good hygiene, such as hand washing, can help prevent infection. It also keeps giardiasis from spreading to others.
- People suffering from giardiasis should avoid swimming in recreational water for at least two weeks after their symptoms have subsided.
- *Giardia* cysts are more resistant to chlorine treatment than other microorganisms, and outbreaks have been associated to polluted mains drinking water, paddling pools and swimming pools. Adherence to guidelines for swimming pool management reduces the risk of giardiasis to a minimum (Minetti *et al.*, 2016).

Conclusion

It is a universal problem that affects individuals of any age but especially the young. Although *Giardia* often does not cause symptoms, diarrhoea is a common symptom, although patients may have less dramatic symptoms of dyspepsia or symptoms that mimic an irritable bowel syndrome. Although not a common cause of non-ulcer dyspepsia, it is eminently treatable. Microscopy or immunologic procedures in faeces, or microscopy of duodenal aspirates or duodenal biopsy specimens, are used to identify the organism. The disease is widespread enough to be considered a public health concern. An EIA is the most useful stool screening test. Endoscopy needs microscopic analysis of biopsies or a duodenal aspirate for diagnosis.

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